

GALILEE PILOT, ISRAEL

8 SEPTEMBER 2022, ATHENS

Prof Uri Marchaim
Uri@migal.org.il

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818496. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The Galilee Pilot

The pilot was implemented in the most peripheral region of Israel, where economic development lags behind the core regions of the country.

Galilee is a
touristic region

It is the origin
of the Jordan

We face that many young people are leaving to the centre of Israel, salaries are lower in Galilee, education and culture are inferior, and life expectancy is shorter in 2 years compared to the centre since no remote medicine is available.

The Galilee region's vision for rural development

We follow the EU approach for stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural area by analysing the specific needs of the region

➤ Stronger rural areas

We examined needs to empower and vibrant local communities.

➤ Connected rural areas

For further development the Galilee is dependent on being well connected

➤ More resilient rural areas that foster well-being

We examined the basic needs for regional economic development, for retaining the youngsters in the region, and improve the health services

➤ Prosperous rural areas

In order that the Galilee will be more prosperous we examined diversifying economic activities, especially upgrading salaries for the young citizens

We examine with stakeholders the needs and directions

Through intensive discussions with stakeholders from the diverse population in the Galilee, organising discussions with stakeholders, workshops and face-to-face meetings with delegates from the municipalities and the different authorities in the region, we defined the problems and the vision that the population is faced with.

Stages in the process in the Galilee

Lessons learned at the PoliRural Galilee project

- There are specific challenges the Galilee face that could lead to economic development
- Young people would like to stay in the region if they can have high salaries and interesting work, and would like to study in Galilee
- There is a need to improve the health services in the Galilee
- Galilee has the potential to be economical prosperous if getting similar investments to the centre of the country
- In order to develop the region economically there is a need to upgrade the digitalisation infrastructure

Examine Four alternatives for the advancement and development of the Galilee

1. Establishment of **The University of the Galilee**, by merging The nearby Colleges and MIGAL Research Institute
2. Construction of broadband or **5G digitalization infrastructure** for the Galilee, for the development of industry, agriculture, health, education and tourism.
3. Continuing the **line of the train** to the Eastern Galilee, investment in infrastructure.
4. Development of the **tourism sector** as a significant field of employment and revenue in the Galilee

As result of the SWOT analysis & Foresight exercise we decided to focus on digitalisation of the Galilee

- The essence of this work is to shed light on the importance of investing in advanced communications infrastructure and their deployment in the Galilee region, while emphasizing the great importance for the future economic development of the region.

- An examination reveals that there are significant gaps in the current and planned deployment of fibre-optics and 5th generation infrastructure between the Galilee and the centre of the country.
- This is due to disadvantages in the viability of investing in communications infrastructure in a peripheral region which is remote, with low population density, and with relatively low economic activity.

The implementation of PoliRural approach in the Galilee

- Based on the activities in the vibrant Galilee region we set up the goals of entrepreneurial activity in the region, which will lead to a frog leap in the sectors of industry, agriculture, research and higher education, tourism, health and well-being. Advancing the region's ability to achieve these goals is one of the focus areas of the “Leading Team”, which was established during the project.
- It was coordinated with the Eastern-Galilee Cluster of Municipalities

Action Plan

To be a successful Action Plan the idea was adopted by key policy stakeholders.

Based on the collaboration with the Eastern-Galilee Cluster of the municipalities we design the action plan, and further discussed it with stakeholders in the Galilee, as well as with people from the Israeli government.

It was obvious that the upgrading of the digitalisation infrastructure of the Galilee region requires a large budget and can only be executed if the Israeli government will define it as a priority, and we will be able to develop a Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) with companies that will be interested to invest.

The Deloitte analysis is, therefore, used for introduction of the measures and recommended steps forwards as presented in the Action Plan, in order to find the resources for more funding allocation.

Preparing an economic analysis

- Deloitte consulting company was selected to perform an economic analysis of the benefits of upgrading the digitalisation infrastructure in the Galilee, in order to present it to the Israeli government.
- We intend to present the economic analysis to the government in order to ask for special conditions for the Galilee region.

Advancing the financial needs for implementation

- We discussed the ways to present the analysis both to the private sector and the government of Israel in order to try and develop a PPP (Private Public Partnership) that could lead to the implementation in the next few years.
- We are discussing it now with the Ministry of Telecommunication and plan to approach the telecommunication companies in Israel soon.

Meeting the Minister of telecommunication in Jerusalem with a delegation of the regional municipalities

Results

- We consider that the most significant results of the Galilee pilot, based on the collaboration with multi-stakeholder from the diverse sector in the region – academia, industry, SMEs, farmers, and citizens, was presenting a new insights and knowledge about your region's main needs for economic development and retaining the young generation in the region.
- The collaboration with the Eastern-Galilee Cluster of the mayors of the municipalities generated the infrastructure to influence changes and present the need to the government.
- The main efforts in front of us is to find the resources.